

Theoretical Usage of Neurotoxins to Treat Neuromuscular Junction Disorders and Diseases

By: Adhith Theyver

Abstract

Neuromuscular Junction Diseases and Disorders pose significant challenges to those who are affected by them. This paper aims to explore the therapeutic use of neurotoxins, Botulinum Neurotoxin (BoNT) and alpha-latrotoxin. We specifically look at acetylcholine and calcium ions and their interplay at neuromuscular junctions. The diseases/disorders that are studied are cholinergic crisis and Lambert Eaton Myasthenic Syndrome (LEMS).

We conducted a thorough review of relevant medical and scientific literature. The information that was attained was used to support claims, draw conclusions, and establish a significant correlation between claims and data points.

Our research revealed that Botulinum Neurotoxin (BoNT) may be able to treat patients suffering from a cholinergic crisis by regulating the diffusion of neurotransmitters into the synaptic cleft. It also revealed that alpha-latrotoxin may be used to reactivate acetylcholinesterase, by providing an influx of calcium ions. It also revealed that alpha-latrotoxin can help treat patients with LEMS by lengthening the duration of a phenomenon called post-activation facilitation.

The final conclusion was that the evidence gathered during this research gives us theoretical means to treat neuromuscular junction diseases and disorders through the application of neurotoxins.

Introduction

Neurotoxins are poisons which act on the nervous system [2]. The musculoskeletal system is connected to the nervous system through a series of neuromuscular junctions. Studying the effect of how neurotoxins can be used to treat neuromuscular junction disorders and diseases should be relevant for several reasons. It can lead to the development of more effective treatments; we will have the ability to alleviate the symptoms and improve the daily functioning of those with neuromuscular diseases and disorders. Some examples of neuromuscular junction disorders are Lambert Eaton Myasthenic Syndrome, and cholinergic crisis. Neurotoxic substances have the ability to cause significant harm to those exposed to them, and if we better understand potential risks that neurotoxins pose to muscular and skeletal health we can create preventative measures and create appropriate treatment strategies.

The main objective of this study is to look into neurotoxins and their close interplay with the neuromuscular junction. In this study, we looked at two specific neurotoxins, Botulinum Neurotoxin (BoNT), and alpha-latrotoxin. BoNT is one the most

poisonous biological substances known, it is a neurotoxin produced by the bacterium *Clostridium botulinum* [1]. BoNT exhibits potential for therapeutic application. BoNT is known for its patient paralytic effects, but when administered in controlled doses it can be used to target overactive muscles. Alpha-latrotoxins are a class of potent neurotoxins found within the venom of the black widow spiders. We specifically look into how these neurotoxins are related to disorders like cholinergic crisis and Lambert Eaton Myasthenic Syndrome (LEMS). These neurotoxins are just a few of the many substances which can affect the musculoskeletal system.

The neuromuscular junction is a synaptic connection between the terminal end of a motor nerve and a muscle. It is where there is a transmission of action potential from the nerve to the muscle. The transmission is carried out by neurotransmitters like acetylcholine (ACh). When a motor neuron is stimulated, an action potential releases a neurotransmitter called acetylcholine into the neuromuscular junction. Upon its release the acetylcholine spreads across the synaptic cleft, which is the small gap between the axon nerve terminal and the muscle fiber [3]. Neurotransmitters are essential for effective communication between the nervous and musculoskeletal system.

This research paper aims to explore the therapeutic potential of neurotoxins, specifically Botulinum Neurotoxin, and alpha-latrotoxin, in regulating neurotransmitter release at the neuromuscular junction. By examining their interactions at the neuromuscular junction we hope to usher the development of more effective treatments for neuromuscular junction diseases and disorders.

Cholinergic Crisis

Cholinergic crisis is a disorder that arises as an overstimulation of nicotinic and muscarinic receptors at the neuromuscular junctions [4]. There are many causes for cholinergic crisis, it includes, an inactivation or inhibition of the acetylcholinesterase (AChE) enzyme, use of certain medications, and exposure to certain toxins. The enzyme AChE is involved with the degradation of ACh into acetyl and choline. When the ACh is not degraded it builds up, and symptoms like, cramps, salivation, lacrimation, muscular weakness, paralysis, muscular fasciculation, diarrhea, and blurry vision arise [4]. Some of the possible neurotoxins that can be used as treatment are botulinum neurotoxin and alpha-latrotoxin.

Botulinum Neurotoxin (BoNT) as a Treatment

During normal transmitter release acetylcholine is released into the synaptic cleft, but when botulinum neurotoxin is present, acetylcholine is prevented from being released. BoNT prevents the release of acetylcholine through its ability to cleave SNARE (SNAP REceptors) proteins. In normal transmitter release the SNARE proteins bind to the synaptic vesicles which contain acetylcholine. After they bind acetylcholine is released into the synaptic cleft. However when the SNARE proteins are cleaved by Botulinum Neurotoxins the synaptic vesicle is unable to exocytosis into the synaptic cleft from the axon terminal [1]. During cholinergic crisis an excessive amount of acetylcholine is exocytosed from the axon terminal, and to prevent/decelerate the rate

of ACh release, BoNT can cleave the SNARE proteins and stop the liberation of ACh vesicles [4].

Moderate amounts of botulinum neurotoxins can be used to treat cholinergic crisis. BoNT has been used to treat various diseases and disorders in the past like focal dystonias, strabismus, and blepharospasm. In this research paper conducted by P K Ingram and Anjana Ingram, BoNT was used similarly to treat dysphagia through cleavage of SNARE proteins [1], [8]. BoNT is used as a therapeutic drug because of its ability to prevent the release of acetylcholine. It has the capability to treat focal dystonias, strabismus, and blepharospasm. Local injections of the neurotoxins weaken overactive muscle and control the hypersecretion of glands. Botulinum neurotoxin does not have permanent effects on the patient it is administered to, instead it allows for nerve endings to regenerate and muscular function to reappear.

By preventing the release of acetylcholine, BoNT calms the overstimulation of the muscarinic and nicotinic receptors at the neuromuscular junction. In the case of the enzyme acetylcholinesterase (AChE) being inhibited, acetylcholine will keep building up in the synaptic cleft, but if a proper amount of a BoNT is used then acetylcholine will stop getting released from the axon terminal. This will give the body time to reactivate the AChE enzyme and bring the concentration of acetylcholine at the neuromuscular junction back to a homeostatic level. If no medication or treatment is used, then even when there is a surplus of ACh at the synaptic cleft, the body will keep on releasing more which will lead to even more dire consequences.

A-latrotoxin as a treatment

Using alpha-latrotoxin to treat cholinergic crisis through the release of calcium ions represents a complex therapeutic approach. These toxins have evolved to induce a massive release of neurotransmitters, acetylcholine, from presynaptic nerve terminals [5]. This uncontrolled release can exacerbate cholinergic systems initially, it will also end up triggering a cascade of events which holds promise for alleviating cholinergic crisis symptoms in the long run.

Even though cholinergic crisis can occur for a variety of reasons, alpha-latrotoxin can only be used as a possible treatment for cholinergic crisis caused by inhibition of acetylcholinesterase.

When alpha-latrotoxin is introduced to the neuromuscular junction, it binds to specific receptors on the presynaptic nerve terminals and can cause a rush of acetylcholine into the synaptic cleft [5]. Even though adding more acetylcholine to a state of cholinergic crisis may seem counterintuitive, as it can temporarily worsen symptoms. However, it also activates the voltage-gated calcium ion channels (VGCC) located on the presynaptic nerve terminal, which will lead to an influx of calcium ions into the cytoplasm.

Calcium ions are not necessarily cofactors of acetylcholinesterase, but they have been shown to increase the reaction rate of the enzyme [6]. Calcium ions have the ability to stabilize the molecular structure of acetylcholinesterase. The enzyme has an anionic site, which is a distinct form of an active site, the positively charged calcium ions

will bind to the negatively charged amino acids that line the anionic site. As calcium is a benefactor for the enzyme, it will increase the enzymatic activity for acetylcholinesterase and it will terminate the cholinergic crisis signal.

Utilizing alpha-latrotoxin presents a complex yet promising therapeutic approach. It should be noted that its use should only be applied when a cholinergic crisis arises because of acetylcholinesterase inhibition.

Neurotoxin Treatment for Cholinergic Crisis: Considerations, Benefits, and Risks

There are various benefits and risks for neurotoxin treatment for patients diagnosed with cholinergic crisis.

Normal medication and BoNT work in the same manner to treat cholinergic crisis, through the prevention of acetylcholine release. Alpha-latrotoxin works like a medication called Pralidoxime, which treats cholinergic crisis through the reactivation of acetylcholinesterase, even though the method of reactivation is different, the principle remains the same [7]. The application of the neurotoxin as a treatment should be controlled and done by a professional. There are many factors that should be taken into account before botulinum neurotoxin is used as a form of treatment. It is highly potent, and if used improperly it can lead to severe neurological and muscular damage. There should be a precise injection technique, the treatment should be contained in the area that is affected by the cholinergic crisis [8]. Also, not all patients will be suitable for neurotoxin treatment. For example neurotoxins can interfere with other medications, so if the patient is using other medicines it is essential to identify that during the patient evaluation.

Even though there are serious considerations and risks, there are also many benefits. There is targeted treatment, which is a contrast to conventional treatment. During conventional treatment healthy cells are also exposed to the medications, but during targeted treatment only a few healthy cells come into contact with the treatment, which allows for fewer side effects. It can also allow for a more personalized care route for the patient. It can allow for prevention of under or over dosage of the drug. Neurotoxins like Botulinum neurotoxin work quickly, so after they are injected they allow for rapid release.

Lambert-Eaton Myasthenic Syndrome

Lambert-Eaton Myasthenic Syndrome (LEMS), is a rare autoimmune disorder of the neuromuscular junction. When LEMS is present, there are autoantibodies which go against voltage gated calcium channels (VGCC) play a crucial role in transmitting nerve signals to the muscles. VGCC regulates the influx and concentration of calcium ions; they also diminish the release of ACh into the synaptic cleft. The reduction of ACh results in inefficient transmission of nerve signals to the muscle [9].

Post activation facilitation is something very unique about LEMS. In the beginning of the autoimmune attack, VGCC are not working in their optimal range; which leads to reduction in the release of neurotransmitters [9], [11]. Neurotransmitters move in accordance to the electron gradient which is altered and controlled by the movement of calcium ions. When the calcium channels are damaged, the NMJ experiences weaker nerve stimulation. Post activation facilitation is characterized by the repeated stimulation of the weak nerve signals; this repeated stimulation causes the build of calcium ions in the nerve terminals. This then directly accelerates the movement of the neurotransmitters, the final product of this process is improved muscular function and stronger muscle contractions with each excessive stimulation. In theory if this state of improved muscular function was maintained; then treatment and overall patient well being will improve drastically

Alpha-latrotoxin as a treatment

A-latrotoxin is a neurotoxin that is known for increasing the concentration of calcium ions in the neuromuscular space [5]. It does this by depolarizing the nerve terminals, and causing an influx of calcium ions. Voltage gated calcium channels are impaired, but a reduced amount of calcium ions can still pass through; which leads to post activation facilitation. In theory if post activation facilitation was prolonged, then treatment will be more simplified and more accurate. Post activation facilitation is characterized by increased nerve impulses; if the amount of nerve impulses are increased then it will extend the duration of facilitation.

Calcium ions can still pass through damaged/impaired VGCC for a variety of reasons [11]. The VGCC will still be able to retain partial functionality, meaning that they will be able to depolarize to some extent and allow calcium ions to pass through. The damaged VGCC may always have a changed threshold for activation; they may require a smaller depolarization to open, allowing calcium ions to enter.

A-latrotoxin does just that; the nerve terminals are depolarized there is an influx of calcium ions; alpha-latrotoxin binds to specific receptors on the presynaptic membrane of nerve cells. Once they are bound to their respective receptor proteins, alpha-latrotoxin induces a conformational change in the receptor protein; leading to the formation of ion channels. During post activation facilitation the threshold for activation for muscle fibers are reduced [10]. This reduction means that a lower concentration of calcium ions will result in activation of the muscle fiber.

These newly formed channels allow an influx of calcium ions into the nerve terminal. This newly discovered concentration of calcium ions will accelerate the movement of neurotransmitters like acetylcholine. Calcium ions will bind to specific proteins in the nerve terminal called synaptic vesicle proteins. This binding triggers the fusion of synaptic vesicles with the presynaptic membrane, which then releases the contents into the synaptic cleft. The released acetylcholine then binds to acetylcholine receptors on the cell membranes, causing the activation of the muscle fiber. This activated muscle fiber will increase the overall function of the muscles that are deprived of stimulation. When more and more contractions come together, the overall effect on the body is positive. The calcium ions released from alpha-latrotoxin causes the

increase in acetylcholine. This then leads to a prolonged phase of post activation facilitation.

The duration of post activation facilitation relies on many factors. One of them being the strength of the initial reaction. The initial reaction is characterized by the muscles' response to the first stimulus. Initial reaction is triggered by the influx of calcium ions, which leads to a more intense and longer initial activation. This is so because the influx has a stronger concentration in comparison with homeostatic levels. This will lead to an overall more pronounced post activation facilitation. Another important factor is frequency of stimulation; this is when muscle fibers are stimulated in a repetitive manner [11]. This then leads to the accumulation of calcium ions. The calcium ions lead to an extended duration of post activation facilitation. Not only does alpha-latrotoxin help usher in post activation facilitation, but it helps maintain it. It completes this phenomenal task in many ways, one being the availability of calcium.

In a research paper by Michal Keogh, Saam Sedehizadeh, and Paul Maddison, 3,4 Diaminopyridine was used to treat LEMS in patients with varying situations. 3,4 Diaminopyridine resulted in an overall positive effect on the people it was administered to. 3,4 Diaminopyridine also helps in the restoration of calcium influx. It does this by blocking some potassium channels on nerve terminals, these channels tend to prevent the influx of calcium ions. When the channels are blocked, calcium ions can enter the nerve terminals more easily. When the calcium ions enter, they are accompanied by an influx of acetylcholine. Most patients were reported to have restoration of neuromuscular function and improved muscle strength [13].

The outcomes and results the patients showed indicate the presence/forecoming of post activation facilitation. Even though it was not explicitly stated in the project; it still did occur. A common sign of post activation facilitations is the return of muscle strength with repeated muscle contraction. In the study mentioned before, muscle strength was regained and measured through myometry. After the 3,4 Diaminopyridine, CMAP (Compound Muscle Action Potential) was measured. There was a general increase in the CMAP levels of the patients (Additional information can be located in the supplemental figure, offering a visual depiction of the relevant data). CMAP is an electrical measure of the summated action potentials of all stimulated motor endplates, it potentially reflects increased muscle contractions [13][14]. The elevated CMAP levels could also indicate the existence of post activation facilitation; a higher CMAP level indicates increased muscle contraction. If there are increased muscle contractions during LEMS; post activation facilitation is alleviating the symptoms and overall wellness of the patient.

In conclusion 3,4 Diaminopyridine acts similarly to alpha-latrotoxin, in that it induces post activation facilitation.

Neurotoxin Treatment for Lambert Eaton Myasthenic Syndrome: Considerations, Benefits, and Risks

If the alpha-latrotoxin is used in wrong proportions, then the increased concentration of calcium ions and acetylcholine can actually have an adverse effect on

the body. Examples of adverse health effects are muscle cramps, nervous system overstimulation, cardiovascular effects, overall weakness, and systemic toxicity [5]. If alpha-latrotoxin is used improperly then the outcome may be worse than the original state of LEMS.

However, there are several precautions and considerations that should be taken into account before alpha-latrotoxin is administered. One is precise dosage, even the slightest deviation from the appropriate amount can lead to serious health implications. Another precaution is appropriate localization; alpha-latrotoxin should be aimed at specific nerve channels and neuromuscular junctions. If patients ever do undergo this treatment they should be in constant monitoring by the medical staff, extreme side effects are definitely possible. Using alpha-latrotoxin as a treatment is just a theoretical idea, and must undergo testing and trials for further information on its ability to trade LEMS.

Even though there is an abundance of precautions, there are some benefits. One being is that alpha-latrotoxin treatment would be minimally invasive; would only require an injection. The neurotoxins doses will be able to adjust to fit with the patient's circumstances, allowing for a tailored approach.

Conclusion

In conclusion, neuromuscular junction diseases and disorders, like cholinergic crisis and LEMS, present intriguing theoretical treatments that involve the application of neurotoxins like botulinum neurotoxin and alpha-latrotoxin. They both can have therapeutic potential by regulating the release of neurotransmitters at neuromuscular junctions and disorders.

For cholinergic crisis, Botulinum neurotoxin has shown promise of preventing overstimulation of muscarinic and nicotinic receptors. Botulinum neurotoxin has been shown that it does work as a treatment for disorders like dysphagia [8]. Alpha-latrotoxin helps reactive acetylcholinesterase by increasing the concentration of calcium ions [5]. The calcium ions will help reactivate the deactivated enzymes. The reactivated enzyme will bring down the concentration of acetylcholine to homeostatic levels.

For Lambert Eaton Myasthenic Syndrome (LEMS), alpha-latrotoxin is used to bring forth post activation facilitation. This will allow the patient to live a healthier life, and will make overall treatment easier. It does this by causing stronger muscle activations. These stronger muscle palpitations help usher in post activation facilitation, and help maintain a state of it for the long run. An extended post-activation facilitation, will result in long-term benefits for individuals suffering from LEMS.

In summary, neurotoxins like botulinum neurotoxin and alpha-latrotoxin show promise in the treatment of neuromuscular junction diseases and disorders. By targeting specific aspects of the neurotransmitter release process, these therapies offer hope for improved managements and outcomes for patients suffering from conditions like cholinergic crisis and LEMS. It must be noted that further research and trials are necessary to harness the full potential of this type of treatment.

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